

Maximum power point tracking of photovoltaic array using fuzzy logic control

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jul 2, 2022

Revised Aug 25, 2022

Accepted Sep 12, 2022

Keywords:

Fuzzy logic control

MATLAB/Simulink

Maximum power point tracking

Perturb and observe

Photovoltaic array

ABSTRACT

This research introduces the simulation of photovoltaic (PV) array to track the peak point (MPPT) using fuzzy logic control. Therefore, real time simulation is performed in MATLAB/Simulink based on a PV model, boost converter and fuzzy logic-based tracker. A comparative study is carried out against perturb and observe (P&O) controller. The fuzzy logic technique based tracker can successfully track the maximum power point very fast and has precise control when compared to the P&O algorithm. The overall we conclude that the MPPT using the fuzzy logic technique takes a fast response and can improve the performance of the PV system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important reasons that pushed them to pay attention to renewable energy sources is its environmentally friendly work and its great availability all over the world [1]. One of the most important energies is photovoltaic energy that is one of the most prominent and most promising energies because it has a clean and inexhaustible source (sustainable) [2]. The photovoltaic energy system converts sunlight into continuous electrical energy by means of solar cells made of semiconducting materials, where the work and efficiency of solar cells depends mainly on two factors; the temperature and solar radiation [3]. These cells have a non-linear characteristic that is evident through a curve output versus voltage [4], from the non-linear relationships of photovoltaic, we notice a unique point in certain conditions of illumination and temperature in which the value of the energy produced is the maximum energy [5]. This point referred to the maximum power point (MPPT) [6]. The decrease in the efficiency of cells is mainly caused by atmospheric differences (change of radiation and temperature) and to improve the efficiency of these cells, there are many MPPT technologies, among them the most prominent and most widespread is perturb and observe technique (P&O). However, this technology has limitations due to the nonlinearity of photovoltaic cells [7]. Incremental conductance techniques are many used in the literature which is relative simplicity of implementation [8].

In recent years, new technologies called artificial intelligence techniques have emerged. Among the most prominent of these techniques is the fuzzy logic technique. This technique is more effective and more accurate in tracking the maximum power point MPPT, as it achieves good and more stable results compared to using perturb and observe (P&O) technique [9]. This paper focuses on the maximum solar energy used fuzzy logical algorithm.

2. MODELLING AND SIMULATION OF 50 W PHOTOVOLTAIC (PV) ARRAY

The PV module is a sunlight-to-electricity conversion technology. In other words, it produces direct current without any noise or environmental effect when a PV module is exposed to solar irradiation. In this paper, we designed a 50 watt PV matrix. The primary building block of photovoltaic (PV) array is the solar cell, which is essentially the p-n semiconductor junction, as described in Figure 1 [10]. The following equations describing the PV model under studied:

$$I_{ph} = \frac{G}{G_{ref}} (I_{ph,ref} + \mu_{sc} * \Delta T) \quad (1)$$

$$I_{0,ref} = I_{sc,ref} \exp\left(\frac{-V_{oc,ref} * q}{N_s * A * k * T_c}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$I_0 = DT_c^3 \exp\left(\frac{-q * \epsilon_G}{A * K}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$I_d = I_0 \left[\exp\left(\frac{V + I * R_s}{q}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (4)$$

$$I_p = \frac{V + I * R_s}{R_p} \quad (5)$$

$$I = I_{ph} - I_d - I_p \quad (6)$$

Where

I : The PV current,

I_d : The diode current current,

I_p : The shunt current,

I_0 : The reverse saturation current,

$I_{sc,ref}$: the current at short circuit,

ϵ_G : the band gap energy of semiconductor

A : diode ideality factor,

q : The electron charge,

K : The Boltzmann constant,

T_c : The actual cell temperature (K),

V : the thermal voltage,

$V_{oc,ref}$: the voltage at open circuit

N_s : The number of PV cells connected in series,

N_p : The number of PV cells connected in parallel,

V : The output terminal voltage,

R_p : The parallel resistances of solar,

R_s : The series resistances of solar,

G : Irradiance (W/m^2),

G_{ref} : Irradiance at STC= $1000 W/m^2$, $\Delta T = T_c -$

$T_{c,ref}$: (Kelvin),

μ_{sc} : Coefficient temperature of short circuit current (A/K),

$I_{ph,ref}$: Photocurrent (A) at STC.

Figure 1. Mathematical modeling of PV cell

Through the photoelectric properties shown in Figure 2 [11]. This point is called the maximum power point (MPP) that we track using the MPPT technique [12]. The 50M (36) module connected in server having a maximum power is 50 W under standard conditions with $G = 1000 W/m^2$ and $T = 25^\circ C$ ($298^\circ K$),

$A = 1.3, N_s=36, N_p = 1; T_{ref} = 298 \text{ °K}(25 \text{ °C}), E_g = 1.12\text{eV}, R_{sh} = 1000 \text{ }\Omega, R_s = 0.1 \text{ }\Omega$. Electrical Characteristics of 50 M (36) PV module are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. I-V and PV characteristics of a PV module

Table 1. Electrical characteristics 50 M (36) PV module

Parameters	Value
Maximum power	50 W
V_{max}	17.98 V
I_{max}	2.78 A
I_{sc}	3.04 A
V_{oc}	21.87 V
K_i	$(0.065\pm 0.15) \text{ A/°C}$

3. MODELING OF BOOST CONVERTER

The modelling of the boost converter is presented in this article before beginning our research on the modeling of MPPT controls. This causes the output voltage of V_s to be increased compared to the input voltage of V_{pv} . The circuit diagram modelling the converter is shown in Figure 3, whereas Table 2 summarizes the values of the elements used to make this converter [13].

Figure 3. The boost converter scheme

Table 2. Component values of DC/DC converter

Parameters	Value
Bobbin L_{pv}	18 mH
Input capacitor C_e	2200 μF
Output capacitor C_s	2200 μF
Switching frequency of the MOSFT f	1 KHz
Load R	22 Ohm

The (7) and (8) show the process of the boosting of the voltage of the PV system:

$$V_{pv} = L_{pv} \frac{di_{L_{pv}}}{dt} + (1 - a_{pv})V_s \tag{7}$$

$$C_s \frac{dV_s}{dt} + \frac{V_s}{R} = (1 - a_{pv})i_{L_{pv}} \tag{8}$$

4. MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING (MPPT)

4.1. P&O based MPPT tracking

In this paper, the P&O algorithm MPPT technique is applied to find MPP in 50 W modelled PV array. The P&O technique is selected in this research due to its simplicity and fast tracking of the maximum point operation of solar system. The flow scheme of P&O controller is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Chart of the implemented P&O

4.2. MPPT by using fuzzy logic

Fuzzy logic is used to extract the MPPT of PV module [14]. The implementation of the fuzzy algorithm, with its controlled rules, is simple and independent of solar characteristics. The rules of the controlled mechanism are shown in Table 3, which contains 49 rules of fuzzy controller.

Table 3. The rules implemented in the fuzzy logic controller

CE	E	NB	NM	NS	ZE	PS	PM	PB
NB	NB	NB	NB	NB	NM	NS	ZE	PS
NM	NB	NB	NB	NM	NS	ZE	PS	PM
NS	NB	NM	NM	NS	ZE	PS	PM	PB
ZE	NB	NM	NS	ZE	PS	PM	PB	NS
PS	NM	NS	ZE	PS	PB	PB	NS	ZE
PM	NS	ZE	PS	PM	PB	PB	ZE	PB
PB	PB	ZE	PS	PM	PB	PB	PB	PB

4.2.1. Fuzzification

Controls are selected depending on the satisfaction of two control variables in the proposed input; they are the E error and the change in CE error in the k-test. We display the E and CE variants in the following form:

$$E(k) = \frac{P(k)-P(k-1)}{V(k)-V(k-1)} \tag{9}$$

$$CE(k) = E(k) - E(k - 1) \tag{10}$$

4.2.2. Inference method

A rule is applied to fuzzy input by the inference engine to determine the fuzzy output. Therefore, the real input value must be fuzzified, before the rule can be evaluated to obtain an appropriate linguistic value [15]–[28]. The rapid changes in the consumption of PV power can be determined by applying minimum perturbation in the output of photovoltaic voltage.

4.2.3. Defuzzification

Defuzzification is the process of obtaining a single number from the output with can, defined by two algorithms; the max criterion method (MCM) and center of area (COA). The block diagram of the operation mechanism of the fuzzy logic technique is explained in Figure 5.

$$\Delta D = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \mu(\Delta D_j) \cdot \Delta D_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \mu(\Delta D_j)} \tag{11}$$

the actual duty cycle ratio D is calculated as follows:

$$D(k) = D(k - 1) + S_{\Delta D} \Delta D(k) \tag{12}$$

The presentation of the error, variation of the error and the change in duty cycle is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Block diagram of fuzzy MPPT algorithm

Figure 6. 3D presentation of the error, variation of the error and the change in duty cycle

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figures 7 to 12. Shows the different output results of the photovoltaic generator simulated using P&O and FL under ($G=1000 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $T=25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Figure 7 shown the Output power of the PV generator for the different simulated algorithms. Where it takes 0.042 s for the traditional Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm to obey the MPP with a major power swing of (50.41-52.39 W). Whilst for the fuzzy logic controller method it takes 0.035 s just and without power oscillation at standard conditions ($E=1000 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $T=25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Figure 10 shows the simulation were presented for many solar irradiance values (800 W/m^2 , 900 W/m^2 and 1000 W/m^2) at fixed temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Figure 10 shows the results of the PV generator for many solar irradiance values (800 W/m^2 , 900 W/m^2 and 1000 W/m^2) at fixed temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. To examine the system. Where we observe the fuzzy logic controller has better response time, much more accurate tracking and less oscillation at each step compared to the classical P&O controller.

Figure 7. Output power of fuzzy logic control (FLC) and conventional P&O controller

Figure 8. Output current of FLC

Figure 9. Output voltage of the controlled techniques

Figure 10. Output power of the tested model

Figure 11. Output current of the simulations of the PV panels

Figure 12. Voltages at different environmental

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this research, FL control is developed for maximation of PV array. We study the MPPT technology based on P&O and compared to FLC. The controller of the fuzzy logic showed fast response and successfully control of tracking the maximum power point (MPPT) considering the effect of atmospheric changes. more than, the MPPT technology based on fuzzy logic control achieves good and more accurate results, more flexibility and eliminates the fluctuations in the power compared to MPPT technology based on P&O.

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